

Synthesis, Characterization and Antimicrobial analysis of Transition Metal Complexes of Thiosemicarbazone Schiff Bases

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19827739

Abstract:

Substituted Thiosemicarbazones and their Transition metal complexes are complexes that possess antitumor, antibacterial, antifungal and antiviral characteristics. In number of cases the reactivity of the ligand is mostly increased by the presence of central metal ion. The most related papers recently published are reviewed with a study to find a relationship between common structural features and activity. These synthesized metal complexes are characterized by CHNS elemental analysis and for their Antimicrobial Activity.

Keywords: Substituted Thiosemicarbazones, Antimicrobial activity.

Introduction:

Thiosemicarbazone are the compounds that have been studied for a considerable period of time for their biological properties. Traces of interest date back to the beginning of the 20th century but the first reports on their medical applications began to appear in the Fifties as drugs against tuberculosis and leprosy [1, 2]. In the Sixties their antiviral properties were discovered and a huge amount of research was carried out that eventually led to the commercialization of methisazone, Marboran, to treat smallpox [3]. In this period one of the first antitumor activity results was published [4]. Recently Triapine (3-aminopyridine-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone) has been developed as an anticancer drug and has reached clinical phase II on several cancer types [5, 6]. Presently, the areas in which thiosemicarbazones are receiving more attention can be broadly classified according to their antitumor, anti-protozoal, antibacterial or antiviral activities

and in all cases their action has been shown to involve interaction with metal ions [7, 8].

Thiosemicarbazone Schiff bases have garnered a lot of interest due to their multifunctional metal-chelating properties, inherent biological activities and structural flexibility. It was established that thiosemicarbazides were metal chelators before the discovery of their anti-tumour activity. In addition to the presence of the C=N and C=S bonds in their own structure, which is favourable for metal coordination, it possesses a flexible thiourea structure that can introduce different substituents or functional groups. The newly synthesized ligands were 2-pyridine formide-N-(4)-methylthiosemicarbazone [9] 2-pyridine formamide-3-piperidyl thiosemicarbazone [10], pyrazineformide –N-(4)-methylthiosemicarbazone.[11] The ligands and complexes were characterized by molar conductivities, magnetic susceptibilities and X-ray techniques. The synthesis of three bis(thiosemicarbazone) compounds formed by

the reaction of benzyl with either thiosemicarbazide, 4-Methyl thiosemicarbazide were reported by Alsop [12]. Gerbeleu [13]

Experimental:

Materials and Methods:

1-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)-4-Diethyl-thiosemicarbazide (LA) was prepared by changing and modifying a reported procedure of Scovil.^[24] Salicylaldehyde were of reagent grade purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All other chemicals were used of AR grade and used as supplied.

1.1-Synthesis of Schiff base ligand (LA) - (1-(2-hydroxybenzylidene)-4-Diethyl-thiosemicarbazide (LA):

Schiff base ligand LA was prepared by mixing together ethanolic solution of N-4-Diethyl-3-Thiosemicarbazide (0.01 M) and Salicylaldehyde (0.01M) in equimolar ratio. The resulting mixture refluxed for 30 minutes. This reaction mixture was chilled (overnight). Yellow colored shiny crystals were separate out which was filtered, washed repeatedly with alcohol and finally with ether.

1.2-Synthesis of Metal Complexes:

Hot methanolic solution of metal salt (1mmol) eg. Cobaltouschloride hexahydrate(0.23gm), Chromium chloride hexahydrate (0.26gm), Nickel chloride hexahydrate (0.23gm) were mixed with hot methanolic solution of ligand (2mmol). The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 1-2 hour on heating mantle. The solid precipitate formed was allowed to keep overnight then it was filtered, washed and dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride in desiccators (Yield-75-78%).

1.3-Physical Measurement:

Microanalytical data of the complexes were obtained from sophisticated test and Instrumentation Centre Cochin. Molar conductance was measured on the Elico (CM82T) conducting bridge. Molar conductance of Cr(III) and Co(II) complexes shows that they are electrolytic in nature while Ni(II) complex is nonelectrolyte. The melting points of all the complexes were determined by open capillary method.

Compound	Molar Cond. (Ω -1 cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Color	Yield	Elemental Analysis (%), Found (Calculated)				
				C	H	N	S	M
LA	—	Brown	80%	64.12 (64.1)	06.36 (05.7)	14.12 (14.0)	09.81 (10.71)	-
[Cr(LA) ₂]	140	Brown	76%	58.95 (59.0)	05.19 (05.2)	12.90 (12.9)	09.81 (09.83)	08.26 (08.1)
[Co(LA) ₂]	120	Dark Brown	75%	58.10 (58.3)	05.10 (05.1)	12.65 (12.7)	09.69 (09.73)	09.68 (09.1)
[Ni(LA) ₂]	029	Yellow	75%	58.01 (58.4)	05.09 (05.1)	12.71 (12.7)	09.72 (09.73)	09.68 (09.0)

Antibacterial and Antifungal Activity:

Thiosemicarbazones and their metal complexes exhibit a wide variety of biological activity. [14, 15] The studies were carried out on *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium oxysporium* species and *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* species using paper disc method on appropriate medium. The susceptibilities of certain strains of bacteria and fungus to the thiosemicarbazone

ligands and their transition metal complexes were evaluated by measuring the size of the bacteriostatic diameter. The result shows that the ligands (HEPT) as well as their metal complexes are more active against the bacteria and fungi and having high antimicrobial and antifungal activity which is almost equal to the activity of standard ciprofloxacin.

Table-2. Antibacterial and Antifungal activity of ligand(LA) and their transition metal complexes. [Diameter of inhibition zone in (mm)].

Ligand/Metal Complex	Antibacterial activity				Antifungal activity			
	Staphylococcus aureus		Bacillus subtilis		Aspergillus Niger		Fusarium Oxysporium	
	250 ppm	500 ppm	250 ppm	500 ppm	250 ppm	500 Ppm	250 ppm	500 Ppm
LA	18	17	26	21	10	21	25	23
[Cr(LA) ₂]	23	21	16	21	19	19	15	18
[Co(LA) ₂]	19	18	29	25	14	20	14	27
[Ni(LA) ₂]	10	15	21	27	25	21	18	26
Ciprofloxacin	34	36	43	45	22	24	31	38

Graph-1. Comparative study of Antimicrobial and Antifungal activity of ligand and its transition metal complexes.

Conclusion:

From the analytical and spectral data it can be concluded that the synthesized complexes are stable. Ligand and its metal complexes as well show very high antibacterial and antifungal activity at both 250 ppm and 500 ppm concentration. In view of the foregoing discussions, the high melting points and insolubility in common organic solvents, also concluded that the three common coordinate sites are phenolic oxygen, azomethine nitrogen and thiol sulphur. It is observed that the Ni (II) complex of ligand contains two coordinated water molecules and possesses octahedral geometry.

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